

HALOPHYTES USED IN AN INTEGRATED BIOREFINERY WITH THE EXTRACTION OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS

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ABSTRACT: Facing the challenge of growing demands for food and energy with a simultaneous decrease in arable land, alternative sources have to be focused on. Second-generation, lignocellulosic biorefineries are being established within the European Union to reduce the dependency on fossil resources by biofuel and bioenergy production. But to cover the demand for sustainably produced foods, energy, and nutraceutical products of biorefineries, the biomass supply needs to be diversified and enlarged. Research is refocusing on existing halophytic plants, which thrive in saline environments. The additional extraction of bioactive compound scan ensures the economic viability of the integrated biorefinery. This review provides an overview of opportunities and challenges faced in the design of integrated halophyte biorefineries, which combine the production of foods and bioenergy with the coproduction of value-added bioactive compounds from lignocellulosic biomass.

Keywords: biorefining, circular economy, second generation, biochemicals, agricultural residues, bioenergy

1 INTRODUCTION

The human population has been using bio-based products and the principle of biorefineries for their supply of foods and also bioenergy for a long time [1, 2]. Production of bioethanol from biomass reportedly started in the late 19th and beginning of the 20th century. Whereas the development of first integrated biorefineries and their terminology has been established during the last decades starting in the 1990s [2].

The general concept of a biorefinery is the production of fuels, energy, foods, nutraceuticals, and pharmaceuticals from different biomass feedstocks [3–5]. In this way, the full potential of photosynthetically reduced CO₂ and water and produced biomass and oxygen are exploited [6]. The International Energy Agency's (IEA) Bioenergy Task 42 gives the following definition "Biorefinery is the sustainable processing of biomass into a spectrum of marketable products and energy (fuels, power, heat)" [7]. Biorefineries can systematically be classified by the description of platforms, feedstocks, products, and processes employed in the refinery [8]. Nowadays, there are already numerous products, which come from biorefineries. The European Union is in its research and innovation program Horizon 2020 funding numerous projects dedicated to aiding the biorefinery vision for 2030 [9].

New synergies are being developed for submerging technologies from biotechnology, chemistry, physics, and food science technologies for better economic performance and maximized biomass valorization [2]. This multidisciplinary concept is relevant for the design of an economically viable biorefinery since sustainable biomass conversion technologies have to be employed [10, 11]. For the construction of a biorefinery concept, especially the investigated biomass composition is of significance.

There is a growing demand for food and energy worldwide, however, the accumulation of biophysical constraints leads to the loss of agriculturally usable land [12, 13]. This is facilitated by climate change and affected areas within the European Union are expected to expand. Especially coastal areas will face susceptibility to increasing areas of marginal land due to salinization. For example, Spain and Italy are already experiencing these

constraints [12, 14, 15]. Estimations from 1989 already considered 7.8 Mha, salt-affected within the European Union [16]. Further, human interference through e.g. poor-quality crop irrigation causes tremendous concern. On this saline land, the cultivation of predominant agricultural plants becomes obsolete [17]. To combat this vicious cycle of degradation of soil being functional as agricultural land and rising demand for foods as well as functional foods is one of the main challenges faced by today's world population [18, 19]. With a focus on covering the demand for sustainably produced foods and energy, against the background of expanding soil salinization, the biomass supply needs to be diversified to secure its accessibility [17].

The question becomes, what can be done to use this land or how can it be regenerated? One possibility is the genetic engineering of predominant agricultural crops to make them more salt-tolerant, but the metabolic pathways are not easy to be altered [20]. In line with these overall circumstances, research is refocussing on the employment of existing salt-tolerant, halophytic plants for agricultural utilization of marginal lands and degraded soils, while minimizing the environmental impact of farming [21]. In contrast to the conventional foods fulfilling human diets, halophytes in contrast to glycophytes, do not require freshwater for irrigation [20, 22]. These salt-tolerant plants are accounting for approx. 2% of terrestrial plant species have diverse definitions. The protective mechanisms, which these halophyte have inherited over time, secure their natural adapting to the conditions by, on the one hand, the storage of salt within the plant. On the other hand, they generate the synthesis of secondary metabolites, which combat the reactive oxygen species caused by oxidative stress in plants, provoked by irrigation with brackish water. These enzymatic or non-enzymatic components are regarded promising valuable by-products of the production of these halophyte species. Particularly the synthesis of metabolites with antioxidative activity or other bioactivities is of emerging interest for application in nutraceutical foods, feeds, or cosmetics [17, 21, 23, 24]. The list of bioactive compounds includes several phenolic compounds [23].

So far, agriculturally solely the fresh edible tips of the halophilic plants have been sold as fresh vegetables. The remaining part of the plant was seen as agricultural waste

because it consists of a lignocellulosic structure in addition to the accumulated high concentrations of salt [25]. For processing, the lignocellulosic structure within the plant prohibits deconstruction, being described as biomass recalcitrance [26]. A new strategy is to use the lignified non-food part of the plant in a biorefinery context, for the extraction of these bioactive compounds and subsequent production of bioenergy. With the simultaneous treatment of waste and not competing with the production of food [27], a sustainable integrated lignocellulosic biorefinery can be designed [19]. Exemplary ancient halophytic species regarded as highly salt-tolerant are *Salicornia* spp., especially *S. europaea*, first described in 1935 [28, 29]. The combination of the exploitation of these specific halophyte traits will furthermore higher the revenue for the farmers as the biomass is valued more resourcefully and less waste is generated. Additionally, the traditional medical application of unprocessed halophytes in human food could in the biorefinery scenario still be exploited. As edible parts of the plant can be valorized before biomass enters the refinery [30].

Additionally, there is a growing market for functional foods and nutraceuticals. Namely, the compound annual growth rate (CAGR) combined for dietary supplements and functional foods is expected to be 9.0 % during the forecast period between 2021 and 2030, starting from a market size of US\$ 454.55 billion in 2021 [31].

This review gives an extensive overview of the state of the art in second-generation biorefineries and what can be done with halophytes in such an environment. This is in line with and part of the AQUACOMBINE project, in which the goal is to establish an integrated halophyte biorefinery. In addition, such a biorefinery will work in line with numerous of the 17 sustainable development goals of the United Nations, e.g. affordable and green energy and responsible production and consumption [32].

2 SECOND-GENERATION BIOREFINERIES

For the design of a biorefinery, the choice of biomass defines the further processing, which products are generated, and the possibilities for bioenergy or biofuel production.

2.1 Biorefinery setup

First, second, and third-generation feedstocks for bioenergy production and biorefineries are distinguished [33]. First-generation feedstocks are based on sugar, starch, or oilseed crops with easier accessibility of energy, requiring fewer processing steps to obtain biofuels, bioenergy, or bioproducts [34]. In contrast, there is the usage of second-generation, lignocellulosic biomass as feedstocks. Those consist of woody biomass, primary residues, or secondary waste from agroforestry [34]. In this case, the advantage is that this biomass does not compete with the production of food. Those plants might be grown on marginal land, as well as not competing with food production, known as the “food vs. fuel” debate [34, 35]. Moreover, food production, through first-generation crops, generates high amounts of greenhouse gas emissions [36]. Some of the main obstacles to bioenergy production from lignocellulosic biomass are the high processing costs, often times making energy production not cost-competitive with the use of conventional fossil fuels [37]. Lastly, there are third-generation feedstocks, which originate from marine resources, mainly algal

biomass [33]. Some authors, such as Yadav *et al.* [38] classify biomass into five groups with the additional categories of “dedicated energy crops” and “halophytes”. Nevertheless, the majority describe halophytes as second-generation feedstock, due to being lignocellulosic, non-food biomass, as it will be categorized in this review, too [39, 40].

Increasing prices in fossil fuels and on the other hand better technologies for energy production from renewable resources are forecasting the transition to biorefineries, replacing the traditional fossil resources, leading to a more climate-neutral economy [41]. This is largely dependent on the supply of suitable biomass and the innovation of efficient, and sustainable processing [42, 43]. Further, besides the processing, also biomass production can lead to greenhouse gas emissions, especially if nitrogen fertilizers are used, which additionally require a considerable amount of fossil energies in production [43]. Moreover, resource depletion of e.g. freshwater, or cultivatable area, are an additional obstacle provoking environmental degradation [36]. Therefore, the trend will shift to second-generation feedstocks for biorefineries and bioenergy production [34]. Even landscape biomass is being considered for implementation in bioenergy facilities [44].

Overall, climate targets are the goal in designing a biorefinery. These are merely challenged by the availability and transport of biomass, the energy consumption of processing, and the downstream processing costs of the final product [34]. The term integrated biorefinery is in this context defined as the incorporation of different processes to obtain a variety of products with the goal of waste reduction. Additionally, modern biorefineries can employ multiple feedstocks simultaneously [45]. Thus, a biorefinery yields a much broader product range in comparison to traditional oil refineries [46].

2.2 What is the current status of biorefineries in the EU?

According to Baldoni *et al.* [47], there were approx. 300 chemical and material-driven biorefineries located in the EU in 2021, registered in the Joint Research Centre Data Catalogue. Of these, 77.3% were applying primary feedstocks and 22.7% were using secondary [47].

Patel and Shah [45] highlighted the major bottlenecks in nowadays integrated lignocellulosic biorefinery design to be the supply of biomass, higher investment costs, and risks in terms of technical immaturity of the complex processes and the risks in scale-up. In contrast to that, the European Union’s strategies are continuously strengthening the development to overcome these start-up burdens [9].

2.3 Bioactive compounds, nutraceuticals, and pharmaceuticals

Bioactive compounds from plants can be used in foods as health promoters, therapeutic agents, and for disease risk reduction. Further, nutraceuticals or even pharmaceutical products can be manufactured from the extracted bioactive compounds [48].

Characterization of bioactive compounds from lignocellulosic biomass and wastes is thoroughly described in the literature [46, 48–50]. Plant biomass’ lignocellulosic intertwined structure consists of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, which are equivalent to be exploited in an integrated biorefinery. While cellulose and hemicellulose are mainly used for bioenergy or

biofuel production, hemicellulose is a resource for lactic acid, xylitol, xylooligosaccharides, polyhydroxyalkanoates, and furfural production. Lignin can be used for the production of vanillin, benzoquinones, and carboxylic acids [45]. Phenolic compounds are described to be important bioactive compounds in plants, while being secondary metabolites, they occur in the non-edible wastes of plants [51]. Either they exist in a soluble form within the plant's cells, being synthesized intracellularly, or they are transported to the cell walls, where they are bound to cell wall molecules e.g. cellulose [52].

If the lipids, antioxidants, or proteins are found mainly bound to the vegetal cell wall, this makes the technical extraction challenging [36]. Equally applies to, bioactive compounds such as phytochemicals, which might be stored within the cell cytoplasm [53]. These immersed locations within the cell matrix, biomass recalcitrance, make the bioactive compounds labor-intensive to be extracted by traditional solvent extractions [9, 53]. Thus, the pretreatment for the extraction of bioactive compounds from biomass is also required to achieve higher yields, e.g. mechanical pretreatment to reduce particle sizes for subsequent solid-liquid extractions, acidification, or thermal treatment [45].

In addition to bioactive compounds, value-added platform chemicals can also be obtained from lignocellulosic biomass [46]. These are displayed in Tab. I. The bioactive compounds are generally higher priced than bioenergy from biorefineries [45].

Table I: Biochemical products and bioactive compounds from the constituents of lignocellulosic biomass [45, 46]

Lignocellulosic Biomass	Production of
Cellulose	glucose, lactic acid, furfural, levulinic acid,
Hemicellulose	lactic acid, xylitol, furfuralxylooligosaccharides, polyhydroxyalkanoates, and furfural
Lignin	monomeric phenols, phenolic compounds, vanillin, benzoquinones, and carboxylic acids

2.4 Bioenergy integration

In an integrated biorefinery, which is based on the principle of a circular economy, there should be zero waste generated. Thus, organic residues from processing are used for the generation of bioenergy, exemplary in form of biogas, i.e. methane or carbon dioxide produced through anaerobic digestion [41]. Another option is the synthesis of biofuels such as bioethanol, or biodiesel [54]. Additionally, biochar can be produced from lignocellulosic biomass residues [55]. Pretreatment performed in previous steps, to extract bioactive compounds, can affect the consequent yields in bioenergy production. This is optimizable in integrated biorefineries, where the produced power and heat are used for the other processes [2, 45].

2.5 Pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass for bioenergy

The separation and fractionation of the lignocellulosic biomass, into its main constituents (lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose) has to be achieved initially. Oftentimes, pretreatment is considered a key step in process

engineering to enhance the yields in the subsequent steps. Through the conversion of lignocellulosic biomass into digestible solids, fermentable sugars, microbiological hydrolysis is improved [56]. Meanwhile, pretreatment is frequently the most expensive, energy-intensive step in a biorefinery [56]. So, identifying cost-effective pretreatment methods of lignocellulosic biomass is one of the key fundamentals for sustainable biorefinery design [45]. In the integrated biorefinery, this pretreatment can either follow the extraction of thermo-labile bioactive compounds or be the prerequisite for extraction processes [2].

Mechanical pretreatment is an option, wherein the biomass' lignocellulosic structure is altered. While being used on commercial scale, this process is energy-intensive. Also available at the commercial scale are acidic and alkaline treatments, and thermal treatments [45].

Pyrolysis is a thermochemical pretreatment method, wherein the biomass is heated to temperatures between 300 and 1,000 °C without the presence of oxygen. It is primarily used for the production of biochar, bio-oil, or syngas [10, 57].

Hydrothermal carbonization is a wet thermal process, wherein the formation of subcritical water is used for pretreatment at temperatures between 180-300 °C and pressure above 10 bar. This process yields treated biomass lower in ash content, which is favorable for biofuel production [58].

The choice of whatever pretreatment method is employed is dependent on the feedstock of the biorefinery and the feedstock may also influence process parameters and subsequent processes [45, 56].

2.6 Emerging technologies in enzymatic/bacterial conversion of biomass in biorefineries

Advances in bioprocess technologies will have to be considered for future biorefinery designs [59, 60]. Especially for thermo-labile bioactive compounds, which experience degradation of their health benefits, if the structure is altered, thus thermochemical extraction methods cannot be considered [36]. Fermentative or enzyme-catalyzed extractions are generally performed at lower temperatures and without organic solvents. These milder processing conditions, i.e. from the enzymatic lowering of the activation energy, are considered to be more eco-friendly than conventional methods [48, 61]. Additionally, the substrate and product specificity of enzymes is promising for industrial application [49]. Problematic in this area are the in comparison to chemical processes, lower product yields, and potentially high costs of e.g. cellulolytic enzymes or microorganisms [60, 62]. Further, potential enzyme inhibitors can be formed during pretreatment or could occur in the feedstock itself [45]. To prevent these obstacles, genetic engineering of microbes becomes essential to make bioprocessing economically competitive, while likewise maintaining low operational costs via the costs of the microbes [61, 63]. Alternatively, the enzymes could be produced on-site in the biorefinery to lower the production costs [45].

As bioactive compounds are embedded within the vegetal cell, enzymes can be employed to enhance the accessibility of extractable bioactive compounds via hydrolytic cell wall breakdown, and enzymatic hydrolysis [64].

2.7 Circular economy in biorefineries

As the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

(IPCC) predicts global warming to become more and more urgent, carbon emissions have to be reduced wherever possible in today's society, and biorefineries have to be analyzed and optimized [6]. The goal is to establish zero-emission and zero waste biorefineries, which supply foods, bioenergy, and value-added health products simultaneously [36]. Potential residues from bioenergy production can be used as biofertilizers or feed to not generate wastes throughout the entire supply chain [4].

Generally, in biorefineries, the economic value added through a product does not correlate with the volume of product generated. For instance, the value generated from energy production is low, although the volume is high, while bioactive compounds are low-volume and high-value. Whether a coproduct is viable is determined via the bioeconomy and production costs [56]. Generally, the opportunity to synthesize bioproducts is the advantage of biorefineries in comparison to bioenergy facilities. Therefore, the co-production of value-added compounds can generate surplus revenue to make an economically profitable, sustainable, and socially favorable biorefinery through the simultaneous creation of jobs [6, 56].

3 POTENTIALS OF HALOPHYTES IN BIOREFINERIES

Halophytes have been described to be the "nonconventional plant resource" e.g. in the production of biofuels [65]. Their reaction mechanism to oxidative stress resulting in salt tolerance is an exceptional advantage, well studied in the literature [17, 29, 66]. As the areas of salt-affected lands will increase on top of the limited availability of freshwater, halophytes will have to be considered. Affected areas of saline soil that are experiencing reduced agricultural yields of non-halophytic plants are displayed in Fig. 1, which was adapted from Stavridou *et al.* [67] and Daliakopoulos *et al.* [14]. Additionally displayed are the areas, where seawater intrusion is experienced [14]. In coastal areas seawater can be used for halophytes irrigation, opening possibilities for cultivation [39]. Halophytes are consisting of a variety of plant families (including perennial species, grasses, small shrubs, and trees) and are already found worldwide, which suggests that cultivation in the context of biorefineries should be feasible [68, 69]. It is additionally speculated that agricultural use of saline land has reduced greenhouse gas emissions in comparison to normal cultivation [70].

In fact, the search for "halophytes" and "biorefinery" in the search engine Google Scholar in March 2022, gives 268 results, out of which 57 are review articles [71]. There is an emerging interest in research and development of these halophyte-based biorefineries as there correspondingly is in lignocellulosic biorefineries [34, 68].

An additional benefit of halophyte cultivation is the reclamation of degraded soil with the accumulation of inorganic salts and heavy metals from the soil in the plants [65].

Figure 1: Impact of soil salinity on the growth of *Miscanthus* (non-halophyte). Legend: blue indicates a yield reduction of >72% [67]; red dots highlight areas affected by seawater intrusion [14]

3.1 Bioactive compounds

Halophyte composition is largely determined by the plant family and species. Flowers *et al.* [72] described 345 species of halophytes to be in 256 families, which survive a 200 mM salt concentration. Moreover, the composition is influenced by whatever abiotic environmental conditions are surrounding the plants, majorly the salt concentrations to which they are submitted [24, 73].

Nevertheless, bioactive compounds in halophytes are gaining more attention. One survival mechanism of these plants is the synthesis of secondary metabolites such as natural antioxidants as phenolics, or aromatic compounds if induced by oxidative stress. These phenolics are bioactive compounds, already employed in a variety of foods, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals. This is based on their additional antimicrobial activity against several pathogenic strains [66, 74]. Qasim *et al.* [23] analyzed the antioxidant activity in a total of 100 medicinal plants, halophytes, and non-halophytes and discovered that the antioxidant capacity and total phenolics content are generally higher in halophytes than in glycophytes. With the elevated phenolic content contributing to the higher antioxidant activity [23]. Aromatic and phenolic compounds in Tunisian medical halophytes have also been analyzed by Jdey *et al.* [74]. They reported biological activity, consisting of antioxidative, antibacterial, and antityrosinase activity. These exhibit the potential for use as a natural ingredient in cosmetics [74]. Overall, wide availability of phenols, including flavonoids, and tannins, as well as proanthocyanidins, carotenoids, alkaloids, and saponins are given in halophyte species, commonly used in rural communities [23].

Besides, halophytes have a promising seed oil composition entailing lipids with bioactive properties [75]. Thus, halophyte biomass has been used in feeds as an additive. The protein content in the seeds is additionally favorable for feed production [68]. Feed trials showed promising improvements in animal health, i.e. in sheep, camels, and cattle, presumably provoked by the presence of these bioactive components [30, 76].

3.2 Extraction methods for bioactive compounds

The accumulation of inorganic salts in halophytes

might impact the efficiency of biomass processing and might cause corrosion on reactor components. Some technologies will require the reduction of ash content to be proficient [39, 65].

The list of emerging extraction methods entailing cascade reactions includes supercritical CO₂, subcritical fluid, ultrasound-assisted, and microwave-assisted extraction with the cascade reactions being anaerobic digestion, fermentation, hydrothermal carbonization, and transesterifications [36]. Specifically for the extraction performed on halophytic biomass, literature is limited, especially regarding industrial-scale applications. Zhu *et al.* [77] describe the solid-phase extraction of phenolic hydroxycinnamic acids (caffeic, ferulic, and protocatechuic acid) from *Salicornia herbacea* L. with ionic liquids as solvent. This extraction followed by methanol extraction and ultrasonic power showed promising results in terms of specificity and sensitivity [77].

Trabelsi *et al.* [66] reported the extraction of biologically active phenolic acids, and flavonoids from the halophyte *Limoniastrum monopetalum*'s leaves by methanol or an acetone/water mixture as a solvent to be promising for the industry. In general, polar organic solvents are regarded most effective for phenol extraction to date [69].

To make use of the bioactive compounds discovered in halophyte plants, extraction methods have to be analyzed and subsequent scale-up for commercial application is mandatory.

3.3 Bioenergy and biofuel production

With an emphasis on plants that can grow on saline lands, there is an emerging interest in the production of bioenergy from second-generation feedstocks [34, 68]. Approximately 9% of the global annual primary energy demand (observed in 2019, [78]) could in the future be covered by biomass production from saline soils, which could result in a production of 56 EJ y⁻¹ [79]. Halophytes could be part of the solution for ensuring sustainable energy production [70].

This is underlined by the elevated amount of literature dedicated towards “halophyte” “bioenergy” in comparison to the previously described biorefinery. Google Scholar gives 2,120 results for this search, in April 2022 [71].

Halophytes have on the one hand oil, especially observed in oilseed producing species, and on the other hand, lignocellulosic biomass, which can be used in energy production [68]. Abideen *et al.* [80] analyzed the composition of the lignocellulosic biomass of different halophytes and concluded, that it consists of 26-37% cellulose, 24-38% hemicellulose, and <10% lignin, making it of good quality for biofuel production. The lignocellulosic residue, regarding the biomethane as well as bioethanol potential, has been estimated to be promising [81]. Halophilic enzymes and bacteria for the conversion of saline biomass could increase the yields and lower the operational costs [70].

Biogas and syngas potential for heat or electricity has also been described in the literature and is an additional option for bioenergy generation in biorefining, as biorefineries require process heat and power as well as fuel for transportation [57, 68, 82, 83].

The fatty acid methyl esters from halophyte seed oil have been reported to have fuel characteristic properties including a high cetane number and iodine value, a prerequisite for biodiesel production [65, 84].

Regarding bioethanol, Bañuelos *et al.* [85] described the yield from *Salicornia bigelovii* fermentation to be promising. The processing comprises pretreatment via wet oxidation and acid hydrolysis and fermentation with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [85]. Halophytes have the potential to be hydrolyzed by enzymes i.e., cellulase, followed by fermentation of the sugars to alcohol. High lignin concentrations are a limiting factor for these biological pathways. In a biorefinery concept, this obstacle can be prevented by the previous extraction of value-added compounds [80]. An assessment of bioethanol production from *Salicornia* species for conversion into bio-jet fuel was reported by Belasri *et al.* [86]. They estimated the energy return on investment to be quite promising for halophyte biomass with a value of 2.4 while producing 3,532 kWh/ha. This is due to low energy inputs for the feedstock supply, outweighing potential drawbacks in energy output [86]. The production of sustainable aviation fuel (kerosene) from halophytes can be performed by deoxygenation and an isomerization and a cracking step (UOP Ecofining™). This production also yields biodiesel and naphtha [87].

Biochar production has been studied and showed elevated ash concentrations in the final product in comparison to biochar from other biomass [57].

Furthermore, research is focusing on conventional breeding methods or genetic approaches for altering the lignocellulosic composition, for improved bioenergy yields via lowering the lignin content, or by increasing the lipid content [40, 80]. Additionally, the production of fillers for biopolymers from halophytes has been described by Batog *et al.* [88]. An overview of bioenergy and biofuel production processes is given in Tab. II.

Table II: Overview of processes required for bioenergy and biofuel production from lignocellulosic, halophyte biomass

Product	Process required	Source
Biochar	pyrolysis	[65]
Biodiesel	crushing, refining and transesterification	[89]
Biodiesel	pyrolysis, hydro treating and refining	[65]
Bioethanol	wet oxidation, hydrolysis and fermentation	[85]
Bioethanol	acid/enzymatic hydrolysis, fermentation and distillation	[65, 89, 90]
Biomethane	anaerobic digestion, purification	[90]
Syngas	pyrolysis and co-processing	[65]

To conclude the chapter about the potential of halophytes in integrated biorefineries, Fig. 2 gives an overview of the described beneficial traits.

Figure 2: Potential of halophyte biomass as feedstock in biorefineries

4 HALOPHYTE BIOREFINERY DESIGN

From the data previously described, the potential of halophytes is unquestionable. But from this point, an integrated biorefinery, including the several industries, being food, feed, bioenergy, biofuel, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals, current status, and future development options are shown.

4.1 Recent developments and opportunities

First halophyte biorefineries in pilot, as well as in larger-scale have been reported, having the main focus on biofuel production.

A 2 ha Integrated Seawater Energy and Aquaculture System (ISEAS) pilot plant has been built in Abu Dhabi to combine the production of *S. bigelovii* oil for aviation fuel with seafood production [39, 87] The estimated yield is

amounting to 900 Liters of biodiesel per ha land [39]. Also, sustainable aviation fuel from this biorefinery was used to operate a first flight in February 2018 [65, 91].

Two larger-sized ISEAS have previously been in operation in Eritrea (1998-2003) and Mexico (2005-2010). Therein, one 340 ha and one 40 ha sized *Salicornia* cultivating biorefineries were installed, producing biofuels. But due to political instability, mismanagement, and societal opposition in local communities as Bailis and Yu [92] reported in a case study, both projects were ended. To overcome these societal burdens, the authors propose third-party monitoring, wherein biological conservation among other implications of biofuel facilities are to be observed. With the additional production of foods, and bioactive compounds the criticism could presumably be counteracted.

Warshay *et al.* [93] performed a life cycle assessment on such an ISEAS for the production of aviation biofuel and compared it to fossil jet fuel usage. The ISEAS renewable jet fuel emits 38-68% fewer greenhouse gas emissions while having an overall positive net energy balance [93].

Meanwhile, the integrated approach with bioactive compounds valorization remains to be established. An integrated biorefinery scheme is displayed in Fig. 3, showing the multiple products possible to produce from halophyte biomass feedstocks.

4.2 Challenges in halophyte biorefineries

Even though there is huge potential for the design of halophyte biorefineries, there are some challenges described in the literature. The halophyte cultivation regarding species and yield optimization has to be evaluated closely and specified for each growth area [39, 94]. Else, the supply of biomass is endangered or too

Figure 3: Halophyte biomass feedstocks conversion to multiple products in an integrated biorefinery

expensive. It is also necessary to use saltwater for irrigation, otherwise, the energy demand for cultivation becomes higher than the energy output, hindering economic sustainability [86, 93]. Further, improvement in mechanical harvesting technology is mandatory, as manual labor is nowadays still required [65]. Additionally, it is not yet known whether industrial-scale production can be impaired by pathogen occurrence, requiring the usage of fertilizers or pesticides [39, 86]. Conclusively, there are uncertainties and financial risks implemented in the transition to large-scale biorefinery designs as process cascades remain to be optimized for biomass respectively [36]. Likewise, the societal uncertainties in the biorefineries locations are questionable [92]. The development of techno-economic models for biorefineries, which include the extraction of bioactive compounds is not yet given [65]. Challenges are displayed in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Industrial-scale challenges observed in halophyte biorefineries

4.3 Modelling of a biorefinery

The heterogeneous composition of biomass, which is widely observed even within the category of halophytes, will make the modeling and optimization an important tool for biorefinery design [95]. In such a refinery, simultaneously different species could be valorized for value-added compounds. Additionally, the process parameters could on-line be supervised and updated to whatever biomass composition is entering the refinery. To further assess the environmental footprint of the biorefinery, life cycle assessment is additionally mandatory.

All in all, the biorefinery design must be seen as a holistic approach with observing each process's influence on further processing as well as on the biorefineries' environmental impact.

4.4 Gaps in the literature

The full potential of halophytes applied in the biorefinery context is not yet fully discovered. Thus, real-life constraints of commercial-scale agricultural production and processing are remaining uncertain [39]. Nevertheless, the described challenges should be outweighed by the perspectives of the transition to fossil fuel-free refineries, namely biorefineries, for the reduction of dependencies on fuel imports [65].

Hence, the AQUACOMBINE project is dedicated to analyze the potential of halophytes and aid the transition to industrial-scale integrated halophyte biorefineries [96].

5 CONCLUSIONS

The emerging requirement for sustainably produced foods, biofuels, and bioenergy around the world could be facilitated by the establishment of halophyte biorefineries. Moreover, the design of an integrated biorefinery enhances the energy efficiency in food, chemicals, and energy production, resulting in a more sustainable, circular economy by supplying a range of products. But, overall, the design of such a biorefinery is complex and consists of many variables, starting from the biomass composition and ending with process engineering, requiring ongoing efforts from companies and governments.

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8 LOGO SPACE

